

CERTAIN ASPECTS OF THE CHEMOTHERAPY OF SYNTHETIC HYPNOTICS.*

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It is a great privilege to be asked to preside at the annual meeting of a learned society like yours, whose chair was previously occupied by distinguished persons like Sir P. C. Rây, Dr. Gilbert J. Fowler and other illustrious men. I have chosen for my discourse a subject which constitutes one of the most important applications of chemistry to medicine and therefore should interest the votaries of chemistry as well as of medicine.

As I stated in my presidential address at the Indian Science Congress last year (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1936, p. 23) the demand for a suitable hypnotic has been intense in recent times, because due to the stress and strain of modern life, many ask for an ideal draught or a tablet or a pill that would gently put them in possession of 'tired nature's sweet restorer, balmy sleep.' From the hypnotics of olden times to recent ones, the chemist has travelled a long way, and he is still moving farther and farther in the search for better hypnotics.

The chief advances in our knowledge of hypnotic drugs in recent times have been (1) the discovery of many new derivatives of the barbituric acid series; (2) the introduction of a number of drugs other than alkaloids for purposes of basal anaesthesia. The barbituric acid derivatives are perhaps the most commonly used hypnotics at the present day. Other recent hypnotics not derived from barbituric acid include avertin, although alcohols, chlorinated alcohols, aldehydes and urithanes have also come to the forefront.

An ideal hypnotic should be free from any toxic effects, should be quickly excreted, give a quiet natural sleep of normal duration in a short time, should give rise to no addiction and leave no effects when one taking it wakes up in the morning. Such a hypnotic has yet to come. Further, the same hypnotic is not suitable for all types of cases and sometimes methods other than hypnotics are suitable for individual persons for relief of sleeplessness.

To Hyderabad the history of hypnotics must have a peculiar interest because the first Chloroform Commission in the whole of the world was held in this great city under the auspices of its illustrious Ruler. Here, as many

* Presidential address at the thirteenth Annual General Meeting of the Indian Chemical Society at Hyderabad, Deccan, 1936.

of you may know, Lauder Brunton made his classical observations on anæsthetics, assisted by Lawrie and others. It was in India again that Waldie, who was one of the pioneers of chemical research in India and who lived in Calcutta, was associated with the discovery of the anæsthetic properties of chloroform in 1847. To his memory there is a tablet in the rooms of the Royal Asiatic Society of Bengal, containing the following words:

In memory of

DAVID WALDIE

Born in Linlithgow, Scotland, February 27th, 1813, David Waldie was associated with the discovery in 1847 of the anæsthetic properties of chloroform. Arriving in Calcutta in 1853, he became the pioneer of chemical manufacture in India. He was an active member of this Society for twentyfive years and served on the Council for ten years. Died in Calcutta, June 23rd 1889.

As pointed out by Willcox, the classification of hypnotic drugs on a purely chemical or pharmacological basis is difficult and unsatisfactory. Hypnotic drugs of low toxicity are alcohols, bromides, etc. A chemical classification of the synthetic hypnotics may be more or less as follows: (1) the alcohols and aldehydes with or without a halogen radical, (2) the urea group, (3) sulphone or sulphone-alkyl group, (4) the barbituric acid group.

Alcohols and aldehydes with or without Halogens.

Chloral.

Chloralamide.

Chlorobutol.

Hypnal, a compound of chloral and antipyrine.

Dormiol, a compound of chloral and amylene hydrate.

Ural, a compound of chloral and urethane.

Isopral is trichloroisopropyl alcohol.

Bromal.

Paraldehyde.

Amylene hydrate.

Aponal, a compound of amylene hydrate and urea.

Hedonal is isomeric with aponal.

Neuronol, diethylbromide acetamide.

Avertin is tribromoethyl alcohol.

The Urea Group.

Urethane—Ethyl carbamate.

Aleudrin—Dichloroisopropyl carbamate.

Uradal or *adalin* is bromodiethyl acetylurea.

Uvaleral or *bromural* or *dormigene* is a monobromoisovaleryl urea.

Somnosal is a proprietary preparation composed of a mixture of bromural and dimethylaminophenylmethylisopyrazolon.

Voluntal—urethane of trichloroethyl alcohol.

Sulphone or Sulphone-alkyl Group.

Sulphonal is dimethylmethane diethylsulphone.

Trional is methylsulphonal.

Tetronal is ethylsulphonal.

The Barbituric Acid Group.

Barbitone or *veronal* is diethylbarbituric acid.

Sodium barbitone or *medinal* is the sodium salt of barbitone.

Proponyl is dipropylbarbituric acid, and

Neonal or *soneryl* is *N*-butylethylbarbituric acid.

Dial is diallylbarbituric acid.

Phenobarbitone or *luminal* is diphenylbarbituric acid.

Sodium luminal is its sodium salt.

Phanodorm is cyclohexenylethylbarbituric acid.

Evipan is *N*-methylcyclohexenylmethyl barbituric acid, and

Sodium evipan or *evipal* is its sodium salt.

Pento-barbitone is ethylmethylbutylbarbituric acid, and its sodium salt is *Nembutal*.

Iprai is calcium ethylisopropylbarbituric acid.

Allonal is a combination of allylisopropyl barbituric acid with amidopyrine.

Veramon, a combination of veronal with amidopyrine.

Gardenal is phenylethylbarbituric acid.

Cibalgin is a combination of dial and amidopyrine.

Somnifaine is a combination of allylisopropylbarbituric acid and veronal.

Sodium hebaral is the sodium salt of hexylethylbarbituric acid.

Beatol is a proprietary preparation said to be a mixture of veronal with extracts of valerian and jusquimane.

Quadronox is a proprietary preparation said to contain 80% veronal, with phenacetin, phenazone, etc.

Amytal is isoamylethylbarbituric acid.

Pernocton is 2-butylbromoethylbarbituric acid.

Sandoptal is isobutylallylbarbituric acid.

The barbiturates conform to the general formula $\begin{matrix} R \\ \diagdown \\ C \\ \diagup \\ R' \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \diagup \\ CO-NH \\ \diagdown \\ CO-NH \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \\ \\ \\ CO \end{matrix}$

where R and R' represent alkyl or aryl groups.

As already mentioned the barbituric acid derivatives are perhaps the most commonly used hypnotics at the present day. When taken by the mouth they are quickly absorbed and within an hour or so after a clinical dose sleep usually ensues.

The addition of alkyl or aryl radicles of higher molecular weight than ethyl adds to the toxicity of the substance, thus luminal, dial, proponal, gardenal, soneryl and nembutal are all more toxic than veronal.

The combination of a barbituric acid compound with an analgesic drug such as amidopyrine, phenacetin, etc. occurs in veramon, allonal, cibalgin, and quadronox and appears according to some to be dangerous since the barbituric acid compound is much more toxic than the analgesic drug, and this may lead to an overdosage of the barbiturate when the preparation is taken in large doses to relieve pain.

Introduction of sodium in the barbituric acid group makes the product soluble. This confers greater speed in action—for example, barbitone sodium or medinal is far more soluble and quicker in action than simple barbitone or veronal. Solubility also makes it possible for one to inject the drug.

The simpler amides are without any appreciable narcotic action, and it is only with the fifth and subsequent members of the series—valerylamide, $C_4H_9 \cdot CO \cdot NH_2$ that any signs of narcotic activity are shown. Aliphatic amides containing longer carbon chains than valerylamide and the next two members of the series show but little narcotic action, so that the range of simpler aliphatic amides showing such activity is confined to those containing the carbon chains, five, six or seven units in length.

The effect of replacing the hydrogen of the CH_3 group of acetamide by alkyl groups is said to increase its narcotic action.

If valerylamide is converted to its *N*-diethyl derivative (1) it does not lose its narcotic activity. This has led to its use in dealing with hysterical or neurasthenic cases.

(I)

The complete replacement of ethyl groups of the *N*-hydrogen atoms in many of the acid amides, as in dipropylacetodiethylamide (II) leads to the formation of compounds without either narcotic or paralytic activity.

(II)

The urethanes occupy a place midway between the simple amides and ureas, and are the esters of the half amide of carbonic acid. They exert a pronounced narcotic action. Ethylurethane (III) possesses a mild narcotic action. Many of the substituted urethanes are more active than the parent

(III)

(IV)

(V)

ethyl derivative. Thus methylpropylcarbinol urethane (Hedonal, IV) has been advocated as a safe hypnotic for general use. The minimum narcotic dose values show it to be appreciably less narcotic than the simple ethyl urethane, but the tertiary butyl derivative (V) is more active. The introduction of halogen atoms, as is general with this type of compound, is attended with a considerable increase in narcotic activity. Thus *αα'*-dichloroisopropyl carbamic ester (Aleudrin, VI) has a minimum narcotic dose value. When the NH_2 -group is substituted by aryl residues as in phenylethylurethane (VII), the narcotic action disappears and an antiseptic action results. Whilst the isomeric unsymmetrical dichloroisopropyl carbamic ester is claimed to be a useful hypnotic (Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 18; *Biochem. Z.*, 1924, 151, 52), voluntary (Linter and Luers, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 88, 122; Willstätter, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 2283) is also used as a hypnotic, supplying thereby a mitigated chloral.

(VI)

(VII)

Concerning the higher aliphatic derivatives of urea a generalisation may be made somewhat similar to that which applies to the active amides namely, that the branched chained compounds are invariably more narcotic in their action than those with normal chains and that a tertiary formation containing a preponderance of ethyl groups favours the development of narcotic activity. Thus, *ter*-butylurea (VIII) is a compound with slight narcotic properties, while the *ter*-amylurea (IX) in which one of the methyl groups has been replaced by an ethyl group produced a ten-hours' sleep in the same animal in a dose of two grams. The replacement of all the methyl groups by ethyl groups as in the *ter*-heptylurea (X) gives a more powerful compound of which 1 g. only was required to produce a six-hour's sleep. It will be remembered that the three alcohols containing the *ter*-butyl, *ter*-amyl and *ter*-heptyl residues (XI—XIII) have also a hypnotic action, and that the

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

magnitudes of their activities are of the same relative order as those of the simple ureas.

The halogenation of acid amides and ureas almost invariably enhances their physiological activity. Among the first instances discovered of this action was that of the increase of activity obtained by brominating diethyl acetamide. The latter compound has only a moderate narcotic action, during a slight stupor, but bromodiethyl acetamide (Neuronal, XIV) has a comparatively strong narcotic action, producing a twenty-six hours' sleep. Similar increases in activity, not so pronounced however, are observed when ethylpropyl and dipropyl acetamide are converted into their bromine

derivatives, whilst the acetyl derivative (XVI) of bromodiethylacetylurea (XV) has a hypnotic action superior to that of the parent body. It is to be noted, also, that the isomer of bromodiethyl acetamide - bromocaprylurea (XVII) is only one-fifth as active as that compound, a fact which further

indicates the necessity of a tertiary hydrocarbon residue in building up hypnotics of this class.

The bromination of valerylamine and its corresponding urea derivative also leads to the formation of compounds of enhanced activity. Thus, α -bromoisovalerylamine produces a fairly deep sleep, and α -bromoisovaleryl urea (Bromural) has been fairly used in practice. Curiously enough, the lower members corresponding to these compounds, e.g., α -bromomethyl-ethyl acetylthiourea and α -bromoisobutyrylurea have but little hypnotic activity.

The question of the effect of the nature of the halogen atom upon the physiological action of compounds in this series, has been investigated in the case of the halogen compounds of iso-valerylurea. iso-Valerylurea itself has a comparatively slight narcotic action, but α -bromoisovalerylurea is a fairly good narcotic producing sleep. α -Chloroisovalerylurea is less narcotic. The introduction of iodine in place of chlorine, giving α -iodoisovalerylurea, appears to destroy almost completely the narcotic action. The simplest cyclic ureas are the hydantoin, concerning the physiological action of which but little is known. Hydantoin itself (XVIII) is physio-

logically inactive, and the $\gamma\gamma$ -diethyl derivative, (XIX) corresponding to diethylacetylurea, possesses a certain narcotic action, which is nevertheless less than the last mentioned substance. The replacement of one of the ethyl

(XVIII)

(XIX)

(XX)

groups by a phenyl residue greatly increases the narcotic activity and gives, in $\gamma\gamma$ -phenylethylhydantoin (XX) a compound which by reason of its prompt narcotic working and freedom from unpleasant secondary effects is used in practice (Nirvanol).

The group of cyclic ureas which have been most widely investigated are the malonylureas, of which malonylurea itself (XXI) is the parent compound. The peculiar ease with which chemical derivatives of malonic ester can be prepared, accounts in some measure for the large number of members of this series of compounds which have been examined.

The narcotic action of malonylurea is insignificant, and can scarcely be said to exist. It is, however, a striking fact that a certain rough parallelism exists between the activity of the malonylureas and of the sulphones, especially in that the methylene group (*) must be elaborated up to a certain size by the substitution of its hydrogen atoms with alkyl groups before the narcotic activity becomes pronounced. Thus, the four compounds methyl,

(XXI)

(XXII)

(XXIII)

(XXII) dimethyl, ethyl and propyl, (XXIII) malonylureas are all without any appreciable narcotic activity. The methylethyl derivative (XXIV) is, however, a mild narcotic, producing sleep, whilst diethylmalonylurea (XXV) (Veronal) is a powerful narcotic producing a deep sleep. The isomeric methylpropylmalonylurea (XXVI) is less active than the diethyl compound, producing only a mild stupor. There is no appreciable increase in narcotic effect when one of the ethyl groups of diethylmalonylurea is replaced by a propyl group, but the corresponding dipropyl compound (XXVII) is somewhat more active. Any increase in size of the carbon chains above that corresponding to two propyl groups is attended by a diminution in

narcotic activity. Thus, diisobutylmalonylurea (XXVIII) produces only a kind of drowsy intoxication. The replacement of simple alkyl groups by unsaturated residues appears to produce only a slight increase in the narcotic activity compared with that of the corresponding saturated derivative. Thus, diallylmalonylurea (XXIX) (Dial) is almost equally as active as the dipropyl compound.

(XXIX)

The effect of various modifications in structure upon the activity of malonylureas shows that for the development of narcotic properties the structural type must be kept within comparatively narrow limits. Replacement of the oxygen of the urea group of diethylmalonyl urea by sulphur, as in thioveronal (XXX) does not appear appreciably to alter the hypnotic activity, although a considerable increase in toxicity is noticed. Methylation of the imino groups acts similarly, giving a fairly toxic compound, (XXXI), while the corresponding dibromopropyl compound (XXXIII) finds use in practice as a rapid and powerful hypnotic.

(XXX)

(XXXI)

The use of a side-chain in which the bromine is attached to an unsaturated carbon atom has been found particularly active in developing the hypnotic activity of the malonylurea series. Thus β -bromopropenyl-propylbarbituric acid (Noctal) (XXXII) has a powerful hypnotic action and produces a six-hour's sleep in proper doses.

(XXXII)

(XXXIII)

(XXXIV)

The opening of the ring malonyl is invariably associated with the almost complete inhibition of the narcotic activity. Thus, even with veronal, the corresponding open-chain compound diethylmalonic acid ureide (XXXIV) is quite inactive.

Amidopyrine.

Attempts to confer pain-relieving qualities on the barbiturates have not been very successful. The closest approaches to a solution which has been made up to the present are the association of a barbiturate nucleus with amidopyrine in Pfeiffer's compound, used in veramon, and the linkage with a member of the morphine group in Didial and Condeonal. Amidopyrine, a derivative of antipyrine, is well known under the registered name of Pyramidon, and appears to possess greater analgesic properties than antipyrine itself or other members of the coal-tar group. Its pain-relieving powers are enhanced by admixture with a simple hypnotic, possibly because the latter diminishes the patient's anticipation of pain. The fact has been made use of in a popular modern series of pain-relieving mixtures which fall outside the Dangerous Drugs Acts.

In each case pain-relief is due to amidopyrine combined rather mechanically or molecularly with a simple hypnotic. A barbitone derivative with pain-relieving qualities in its own right is still to be found.

Up to recent times, the derivatives of amidopyrine were considered to be of low toxicity. Recent observations have shown that they are responsible for an almost fatal condition known as agranulopenia. They have, therefore, to be used with very great caution.

The Margin of Safety in a Hypnotic.

The actual potency does not concern us much. It is just as easy to give five grains of one drug as one grain of a more potent one. The point of practical importance is the margin of safety between the hypnotic dose and the lethal one. This is represented by the ratio M. L. D./M. Th. D. The higher this figure, the safer the drug. Quoting from the literature : luminal is 1·3 ; barbitone 1·6 ; soneryl, nembutal and phanodorm, 2·4 ; dial, 2·5 ; evipan, 5. From this it would appear that it is not very safe to employ luminal in full hypnotic doses, although in sedative or anti-epileptic dosage it is free from immediate risk.

Duration of Sleep to be Expected.

The effect of a sleeping draught should last many hours, but die away before morning. For a basal anæsthetic a much shorter duration is desirable. Quoting once more from available literature :—Human therapeutic dosage : sodium evipan, intravenous, lasts twenty minutes and evipan by mouth, two hours. Rats with coma dosage : nembutal, four and a half hours, pernocton, five hours ; amytal, six to thirty hours ; barbitone, eighteen to thirty-six hours. The duration of narcosis produced by the dial group lies between the evanescent basal anæsthetics and that of drowsy barbitone

itself. As judged by these two considerations of safety and duration alone the basal anæsthetics of choice are evipan and nembutal. Practical experience appears to justify this conclusion.

In 1927 a paper was read by Dr. F. A. Pickworth in which it was shown by animal experiments that actual degenerative changes occurred in the nerve-cells after the prolonged administration of barbituric acid compounds. This work had been carried out by the late Sir Frederiek Mott in conjunction with Dr. Pickworth. There is, therefore a pathological basis for the toxic nervous symptoms which are observed clinically.

In the stage of intoxication which precedes narcosis susceptible patients show excitement, which may hinder rather than promote sleep. The preventive for such trouble is a preliminary dose of bromide. In certain cases, therefore, bromine has been introduced into the barbiturate nucleus—for example, noctal, pernocton.

There are many urea derivatives other than the malonylureas, and some of them are first class hypnotics. They are not barbiturates, and are particularly useful for patients with idiosyncrasies and for those who have become habituated to barbiturates.

May I now refer to the hypnotic properties of the extracts from the root of *Rauwolfia Serpentina*. As early as March 1912, the speaker read a note on its alkaloidal principles and therapeutic properties in a meeting of the Asiatic Society of Bengal. The extracts have marked hypnotic properties and are specially indicated in certain forms of insanity. Since the above paper was read, much work has been done on the chemistry of the drug and many alkaloids have been extracted from the roots. Its hypnotic properties may be due to these alkaloids.

It would be more in keeping with the dignity and traditions of the profession of medicine and chemistry if independent pharmacological research could be endowed in our medical schools and universities sufficiently well to enable us to make our own discoveries. The credentials of every new hypnotic should be carefully examined before a single dose is prescribed.

Now I come to the end of my address and in doing so, I cannot help referring to the various accomplishments, the courteous and unassuming manners, the warmth and benevolence of heart which distinguish the gentleman who has been nominated by the Council to succeed me in this chair and I rejoice most sincerely that the Society possesses amongst its members a person who, is so well qualified to preside over our meetings, to watch over our interests and help us in our deliberations, and who has won for himself a high international reputation for his researches. May our Society prosper under the presidentship of Dr. J. C. Ghosh.